

Non-Faradaic Electrolysis: Concurrent Migration of Nitrogen and other Electroneutral Molecules during Electrolysis

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Low current electrolysis of sufficiently dilute solutions was previously shown by the author to exhibit a number of non-Faradaic features. It is now reported that when such electrolysis is carried out in a cell arrangement wherein the electrolyte in the non-electrode region is exposed to an atmosphere of some electroneutral molecules for example, nitrogen, argon, etc., another highly unexpected feature is observed in addition to the usual non-Faradaic anomalies. A considerable volume of nitrogen or argon migrates away from the non-electrode region and gets liberated with the electrode gases. Besides, a non-stoichiometric mixture of hydrogen and oxygen of comparable volume is simultaneously liberated in the region from where the nitrogen or argon migrates out.

IN course of our studies on non-Faradaic or anomalous electrolysis^{1,2} where the results were found to be very different from what is expected from Faraday's law, it was observed that the cathode gas as well as the anode gas was not only a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen but there was always some nitrogen in both of them, the latter containing proportionately much more than the former. Though it was thought at the beginning that this nitrogen must have been bubbled out by the electrolytically liberated gas from solution which contained dissolved nitrogen from air, it became increasingly apparent as hundreds of results became available that probably nitrogen for some unknown reason had a tendency to migrate with current particularly to the anode under conditions of anomalous electrolysis. Some critical experiments were made and it was found to be a general phenomenon for almost all neutral molecules to migrate concurrently with electrolysis, more so under conditions of anomalous electrolysis. The present note makes a preliminary report of this hitherto unsuspected migration behaviour.

Experimental

Electrolysis in Open Tray i.e., with Access of Air: Our initial experimental set-up which gave us a definite clue of this kind of transport, is shown in Fig. 1. Two tubes T_1 and T_2 containing two platinum foil (1 cm × 1 cm) electrodes and totally filled up with the electrolyte under study were kept suspended in the electrolyte solution contained in an open tray B. In some experiments the immersed ends of the two tubes, either or both, were tightly covered by cellophane membranes.

A solution of sodium sulphate ($N/1000$) was used as the electrolyte, and electrolysis was carried out at 1 mA. Normally, this is the condition very

favourable to anomalous electrolysis^{1,2}, and in a U-tube should show the various anomalies including co-liberation (liberation of a mixture of hydrogen and oxygen) to a strong degree. Some typical results are shown in Table 1. The following features are noticeable from the table (V_C & V_A are the actual volume of gas liberated in the cathode and anode respectively irrespective of their composition).

- (1) There is not much of a deficit in V_C but a strong deficit in V_A as a result of which the overall V_C/V_A value is in the neighbourhood of 3 or higher instead of the expected value of 2.
- (2) However, the results with such an open tray were quite different as far as co-liberation is concerned. The cathode gas was found to be mainly composed of hydrogen with a very small quantity (less than 5%, usually less than 2%) of oxygen, while the anode gas was found to be composed of only oxygen with no trace of hydrogen. Of course, both the gases contain nitrogen (see next para). This is in sharp contrast with the co-liberation behaviour in a closed cell, say a U-tube (vide Table 1) where V_C as well as V_A would have been explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen plus a little nitrogen from dissolved air.
- (3) The third and the most important point to note in the present context is that V_C as well as V_A contains a large amount of nitrogen; nitrogen in V_A is percentagewise much larger than in V_C and may sometimes become as high as the oxygen content.

The question naturally arises about the source of the nitrogen in the liberated gases. This nitrogen could not possibly have come from the dissolved

TABLE I

Cell type	Electrolyte	Current	Cathode gas%				Anode gas%			V_C/V_A	
			V_C/V_{FC}	H ₂	O ₂	N ₂	V_A/V_{FA}	H ₂	O ₂		N ₂
Open tray (Tube length 30 cm, Diam. 28 mm O.D.).	0.001(N)Na ₂ SO ₄	1 mA	~100	81.0	1.2	17.8	53.3	Nil	63.7	36.3	3.75
	„	1 mA	~100	77.8	5.6	16.6	54.7	Nil	58.2	41.8	3.66
U-tube (Height 30 cm., Diam. 32 mm., O.D.).	„	1 mA	86	69.0	24.0	7.0	59.5	38.7	57.9	3.4	2.89

Fig. 1

nitrogen by simple bubbling out by the liberated gas because in that case V_C and V_A would contain more or less similar percentage of nitrogen which is actually not so. Besides, the volume of solution above the electrode through which the electrolytically liberated gas bubbles through can not contain the large amount of nitrogen continuously liberated

on prolonged electrolysis for days and weeks. We hence conclude that nitrogen dissolving from the air in the electrolyte contained in the open tray were somehow being transported to and liberated at the electrodes, proportionately more so at the anode. Further experiments were done to prove this conclusively as described below.

Electrolysis under Nitrogen: The apparatus is shown in Fig. 2. The cell is a 500 ml conical flask in which two arms have been fused in. For brevity such flask will be called Kirtan flask (as it has the appearance of a person doing kirtan (i.e., chanting "Hare Krishna"). A measured volume of nitrogen was kept enclosed above the solution in the Kirtan flask. On electrolysis over a few days it was found that the level L of solution inside the Kirtan flask slowly went down with the progress of electrolysis. On analysis of the residual gas it was found that some nitrogen had left this chamber and this has been more than compensated by some oxygen and hydrogen being liberated into this chamber during electrolysis. The amounts of gas involved as above are quite large as shown in Table 2. These results conclusively prove that nitrogen can get transported by an electric current to the cathode and the anode, proportionately more to the latter under conditions of anomalous electrolysis.

It is to be specially noted that not only nitrogen migrates out of the intermediate zone during electrolysis, hydrogen and oxygen are liberated in the same intermediate non-electrodeic zone in large quantity.

These two peculiarities are however less strongly developed with increase of current (vide Table 2). It might be pointed out that such development of anomaly at low current is a characteristic of non-Faradaic electrolysis¹.

Migration of other Substances Besides Nitrogen: The most unexpected phenomenon of transport of nitrogen by electric current being demonstrated as above, we naturally examined also a few other gases. We have confirmed this behaviour of non-electrolytic migration with a number of other gases. They are hydrogen, methane and argon. Argon is found to be highly transportable much more than nitrogen under the same condition (vide Table 2). We have yet to try other gases, as and when available. Non-electrolytic solutes which are not gaseous such as benzene, sugar, etc. also show such anomalous migration behaviour. Details will be published later.

Theoretical Consideration: Though it is very difficult to think of any mechanism of transport of nitrogen or argon, we believe that such transport is intimately bound with the behaviour which we

Fig. 2

TABLE 2

Electrolyte	Current	Cathode gas %				Anode gas %				V_C/V_A	Gas added	Intermediate Zone gas				
		V_C/V_{FC}	H ₂	O ₂	X*	V_A/V_{FA}	H ₂	O ₂	X*			Initial vol. of the gas c.c.	Final vol. of the gas c.c.	H ₂ in the final gas %	O ₂ in the final gas %	Volume of gas transported c.c.
0.001(N) Na ₂ SO ₄	1 mA	80.8	51.0	15.7	33.3	12.0	15.0	35.0	50.0	13.45	Nitrogen	193.0	248.4	19.2	16.4	33.0
"	10 mA	~100.0	77.9	13.5	8.6	64.6	11.6	70.9	17.5	3.09	"	192.4	213.8	8.9	9.4	17.8
"	10 mA	~100.0	79.7	9.3	11.0	81.2	9.4	69.7	20.9	2.46	Argon	194.6	199.2	8.6	11.7	36.0

* X stands for gases other than hydrogen and oxygen. (i. e. nitrogen)

have termed non-Faradaic or anomalous electrolysis. It is suggested that atoms, molecules or cluster of molecules say of hydrogen become free radical anions by combining with electrons at cathode and these ion radicals on their way to the anode get involved in electron transfer reactions with nitrogen or argon in the intermediate zone. The resultant negatively charged molecules of nitrogen or argon as the case may be, then migrate to the anode. The reverse of above happens with oxygen at the anode which causes migration of say nitrogen to cathode. Not only hydrogen and oxygen but cluster of water molecules may thus get charged and interact with nitrogen or argon on the way eventually carrying them to be electrodes. It is conceivable that such clusters contain charged nitrogen molecules and oppositely charged water

molecules all bound together as a micelle, the net charge determining its transport behaviour. If this be the case the amount transported may not have any relation to Faraday's law. A detailed mechanism of such novel transport has to await further investigations. Further work is in progress.

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References

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